

Fisheries; socio-economics, ecosystems, and ocean carbon in the Celtic Seas

27th March 2024, 10.00 – 18.00 CET/09.00 – 17.00 GMT

Online Workshop

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Mission Atlantic Website: <https://missionatlantic.eu/>

Stakeholder Sign-Up Sheet: <https://tinyurl.com/OceanICUsignup>

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Executive Summary

The Marine Institute hosted an online stakeholder workshop, on the 27th March 2024. This workshop focussed on the Celtic Sea shelf fishing community and (i) its interactions with ocean carbon, (ii) the connections, impacts and potential socio-economic consequences in relation to offshore renewable energy and marine protected areas. It was attended by 19 participants.

The workshop had a dedicated half-day to discuss ocean carbon and its interaction with fisheries. Before the workshop, a survey on initial perceptions of the interactions of ocean carbon, climate change, and fisheries was sent to participants. At the workshop, a series of presentations introduced the OceanICU project, an overview of the pre-workshop survey results, and a 'primer' on ocean carbon. Time was provided for open discussion (Q&A) around the topics presented. This was followed by an interactive session around an ocean carbon and fisheries social-ecological system.

Key topics that emerged can be covered the following themes:

- **Importance of Blue Carbon Habitats:** The role of the ocean and the ecosystem services provided by habitats in sequestering carbon need to be recognised, along with the implications of loss and damage to blue carbon habitats for biodiversity and climate change.
- **Fisheries and Climate Change:** The impacts of climate change on fisheries, how carbon will affect the food web and the implications of these changes for fisheries, and how fisheries can adapt to climate change.
- **Food security:** The role of fishing in providing food security needs to be fully recognised. Management of ocean carbon need to be balanced against the seafood service fish and fisheries are providing (trade-offs).
- **Climate Policy:** Changing policies relating to ocean carbon have wide ranging implications affecting eNGOs, management, as well as the fishing industry.
- **Offshore Renewable Energy:** There are currently high levels of uncertainty relating to ORE. For example, spatial displacement of fishing and shipping vessels may have implications for carbon (e.g. through having to travel further).
- **Livelihoods and Communities:** The potential impacts on particular groups (inshore fishers, trawlers) and on local coastal communities require consideration and consultation in the development of carbon management and policy.
- **Key Knowledge and Evidence Gaps:** Research is required to address the many knowledge gaps remaining relating ocean carbon, for example the lack of consistent evidence on the effects of seabed trawling on carbon, and the uncertainty on how potential impacts resulting from marine activities, may relate to the global carbon cycle.

The second part of the meeting focussed on building a socio-economic conceptual model to capture the potential interactions and impacts of offshore renewable energy, marine protected areas, and fisheries. The resulting model will help to improve our understanding of how fishing, ORE and conservation may interact to create socio-economic impacts and outcomes.

The discussions surrounding the exercises will inform the ongoing research trajectories in the OceanICU and Mission Atlantic projects. Future results and outcomes will be reported back to the participants and wider stakeholder group.

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1. Workshop Goals and Set-Up

1.1 Goals

The relationship between fishing activity and ocean carbon is complicated and somewhat controversial. The ocean takes up about 25% of the carbon we add to the atmosphere, slowing climate change. Various things affect this uptake, yet the overall relationship between fishing, marine carbon and climate change are not well known or understood. OceanICU, a Horizon Europe international collaborative project, is working to address these issues. OceanICU focuses on improving understanding of the interactions and potential effects of industrial fishing on ocean carbon, and assessing if those effects are large enough to affect with ocean carbon uptake and climate change.

This report details the first stakeholder workshop with shelf seas fishery stakeholders as part of this project. The goal of this workshop was to document stakeholder understanding of the links between shelf seas fishing and ocean carbon.

To achieve ecosystem-based marine management, managers and policy-makers must know the full range of factors affecting ecosystems. Integrated ecosystem assessments (IEA) are an approach intended to integrate all components of an ecosystem, including climate change, industrial pressures, society and the economy. At a previous [Mission Atlantic](#) workshop, it was recognized that a large part of the stakeholder concerns in relation to offshore renewable energy, marine protected areas and fisheries relate to the potential and/or anticipated socio-economic impacts. As such, this workshop worked with the attendees to expand upon and better understand the connections, impacts and potential socio-economic consequences through conceptual modelling to inform the wider modelling efforts within the project. It was also an aim to identify relevant data streams and/or indicators that could be used to inform this work.

1.2 Intended Outcomes

The workshop aimed to identify knowledge gaps, areas of interest or need, and potential vulnerabilities and opportunities for intervention relating to shelf sea fisheries and ocean carbon. This was achieved through carrying out interactive exercises including a pre-workshop survey, live brainstorming, open discussion and the co-production of a mental model of the fisheries-carbon system, including the elements that should be included in such a system, and the types of links between those elements.

The workshop also aimed to understand the connections, impacts and potential socio-economic interactions around offshore renewable energy, marine protected areas, and fisheries, building on previous work of the Mission Atlantic project.

The outcomes will inform the direction of our research going forward in OceanICU and Mission Atlantic projects, specifically feeding into developing future scenarios and management/policy questions that are relevant to stakeholder needs, attempting to fill knowledge gaps, and providing input to the development of decision support tools and outputs from the projects. We intend to build on the outputs of this workshop with future stakeholder engagement events and workshops.

1.3 Meeting Set-Up

The meeting was hosted online via teams with collaborative notetaking via a Google document. Participants were provided with a participant information sheet and asked to fill in a consent form in advance of the workshop to comply with GDPR and good ethical scientific practice.

In advance of the workshop, participants were invited to fill out a survey on ocean carbon which gathered some of their initial perceptions of ocean carbon and the links with climate change and fishing. Results were presented at the meeting.

The meeting was recorded for note-taking purposes only. Chatham house rules (information disclosed during a meeting may be reported by those present, but the source of that information may not be explicitly or implicitly identified) was used to ensure open dialogue. Participants were encouraged to contribute with respect in whichever way they were comfortable to do so (speaking up, posting in the Teams chat, or writing directly in the notes document). Additional resources were provided to participants via Google Docs and were available for editing/contributing one-week post-meeting.

The OceanICU project, goals and some background on ocean carbon were presented to provide context and ensure a common starting point. The Mission Atlantic conceptual model was also presented as the starting point for the exploration of socio-economic interactions in relation to offshore renewable energy, marine protected areas, and fisheries.

1.4 Participant Profile

A total of 21 individuals engaged with the survey and/or workshop. 19 attended the workshop (Figures 1.1, 1.2), with 13 people having completed the survey in advance of the workshop. The workshop was attended by representatives from NGOs, managers and responsible authorities, advisory bodies, the fishing industry and their representatives, and academia (Figure 1.2). Participants from NGOs had the greatest representation at the workshop, forming 42% of the group, followed by those from responsible authorities/management, at 21% of the group.

Figure 1.1 Participant profile of attendees at the workshop¹. Fishing industry includes fishers, producers and their representatives. Participant profile of the survey responses varies slightly from this².

¹ One additional individual attended the workshop but was not present for the work presented here, and is therefore not included in this count, this person was from management/responsible authority.

² Two individuals (1 from Fishing industry and 1 NGO) completed the survey but did not attend the workshop. Eight people (3 Advisory Body, 2 NGO, 2 Fishing Industry and 1 Academic/Research) attended the workshop but did not complete the survey. Survey participant profile was: Fishing Industry: 1 individual, 8%; Management/Responsible Authority: 4 individuals, 31%; Academic/Research: 1 individual, 8%; Advisory Body: 0 individuals; NGO: 7 individuals, 54%.

Figure 1.2 Shelf Seas Fisheries Attendees and Survey participants (for terms see glossary, Appendix 8.2)

2. Introduction to Ocean Carbon and Fisheries

2.1 The OceanICU project

Dr Debbi Pedreschi gave an introduction to the OceanICU project. OceanICU is a Pan-European project funded by Horizon Europe and UKRI running from November 2022 to October 2027. It has a consortium of 31 partners across 15 countries. The overall project aim is to produce new data, information and understanding on the role of the ocean in the global carbon cycle. Demands for ocean resources such as food from fish, materials such as trace metals, and blue energy (wind, wave, tidal) are increasing. These increasing demands may affect the uptake of carbon by the ocean due to changes in emissions, industrial processes, and climate change itself. OceanICU recognises the need for knowledge and tools to support decision makers, managers, and ocean users manage ocean resources, and understand how their interactions with the ocean may affect ocean carbon and hence climate change.

OceanICU is developing new tools that include parameters relevant to management and industry (Figure 2.1). As such, we aim to establish current understanding, perceptions, and needs of stakeholders in relation to oceanic carbon and identify key emerging threats and trajectories. This information will then be used to define scenarios of interest and societal relevance for use in a decision-support tool (DST), and to inform an oceanic carbon risk assessment to enable identification and prioritization of societally relevant carbon-related impacts and threats, scenarios, and trade-offs, and their impacts on associated ecosystem services. As part of this, we will produce a multi-sectoral, multi-pressure oceanic carbon risk assessment to enable identification and prioritization of societally-relevant carbon-related impacts and threats, and their impacts on associated ecosystem services.

Figure 2.1 Overview of processes considered in the OceanICU project.

2.2 Links between ocean carbon and shelf seas fisheries

Prof. David Reid and Dr Fiona Culhane introduced some of the relevant points concerning the links between ocean carbon and shelf seas fisheries. Shelf seas sediment store around 11.5% of ocean carbon stocks (Atwood et al., 2020). Shelf and coastal waters provide about 90% of global fish catches (Pauly et al., 2002).

The key themes addressed in this part of the workshop were:

- Fish and the biological carbon pump
- Carbon emissions from fuel use in fishing
- Fishing and carbon release from the seafloor
- Emerging/expanding industries that have a role in relation to carbon or climate change

Prof. Reid described our current understanding of where organic and inorganic carbon is stored in the ocean. He emphasised that the amount of carbon stored in all marine biomass is small (5Gt), compared to e.g. 2200Gt stored in marine sediments (ICES, 2024). Despite this relatively small amount of stored carbon, marine animals can sequester much more (800Gt) through respiration, migration and faecal matter (Pinti et al., 2023). 35% of this 800Gt is by mesopelagic fish.

The emissions from fuel use in fishing are reasonably well understood from the available data. Different types of fishing have different fuel use intensities (Parker in Ziegler & Hornborg, 2023). There are also numerous ways to improve fuel use efficiency, e.g. through using low drag gears, changing fishing behaviour, making engines more efficient, using green fuels, and maintaining healthier fish stocks.

Current research on the impact of bottom trawling on the release of carbon from sediments was also discussed. This is an emerging area of research which is creating some contention. While it is generally accepted that bottom trawling can cause the release of carbon from sediments, there is no consensus on what the extent of this is. For example, Sala et al., (2021) reported that bottom trawling releases the equivalent of 15-20% of atmospheric CO₂. However, using different modelling assumptions, Hiddink et al. (2023) found this to be over-estimated by two to three orders of magnitude. Another study by Epstein et al., (2022) carried out a review that showed mixed results in sediment organic carbon stocks following trawling disturbance.

2.3 Future trajectories

Dr Culhane presented some of the emerging industries that may interact with ocean carbon and shelf seas fisheries. These activities are developing in the context of food security, green-technology, and on-going climate change trajectories. Emerging industries include the potential development of offshore renewable energy (ORE) and industrial Carbon Dioxide Removal (CDR).

Interactions between fisheries, ocean carbon and emerging industries have implications for ecosystem service trade-offs including in relation to food security and fishing livelihoods; green technology; both natural and enhanced carbon capture and storage; as well as nature for nature's sake and biodiversity.

2.4 Ocean Carbon and Fisheries Discussion

Participants questions and comments are given in an anonymised form in black text. The response from the Marine Institute (MI)/OceanICU researchers is given in blue. In some cases, additional information has been added since the workshop, this is indicated in *italics*.

- What role do large marine mammals such as whales play in this? Whales can act as carbon pumps, they feed on the surface but travel much deeper. They can be locally important but globally they are not hugely important in terms of Gigatons of carbon sequestered. Whales produce soluble faecal matter; there are OceanICU researchers specifically investigating whale contributions to the carbon cycle, including faecal matter.
- Is it possible to end up in a situation where we have a hierarchy of species to target in relation to their place in the carbon cycle? In theory, it is conceivable that fish or certain parts of the food-web could be targeted in relation to their role in the carbon cycle. For example, fishing predatory fish (e.g. hake) could lead to more forage fish and larger biomass of fish in general. Would targeting predators be very different from current/historical practices? More speculative examples: substrate type may lead to restricted fishing in certain areas, MPAs could be specified for carbon, etc. However, just because something is conceivable doesn't mean it is likely. Right now, we are collecting baseline knowledge. We can investigate hypothetical scenarios in our models.
- In relation to the effects of trawling on carbon and the different studies that have been published, are they technical or physical studies, or just models? There are some physical studies with sampling of sediment to determine how carbon is affected based on physical evidence. Some do survey carbon, but the big headline papers [Sala, Hiddink] are primarily based on modelling and not physical evidence.

3. Results: Ocean Carbon and Fisheries

3.1 Pre-Workshop Survey

A survey consisting of 14 questions about ocean carbon and 6 questions about the respondents was distributed online in advance of the workshop as part of the formal registration process for the workshop. The survey was hosted on the platform SurveyMonkey. It was designed to get initial perceptions and understanding of ocean carbon, prime the participants to start thinking about the links between fishing and ocean carbon, and assess potential knowledge gaps to prepare presentations for the workshop itself.

The first question asked what people think of when they hear the term ‘ocean carbon’ (Box 3.1). OceanICU takes the starting point that the ocean plays a crucial role in regulating the global climate, by taking up 25% of atmospheric CO₂ and by storing large amounts of carbon, much of it through the processes of the Biological Carbon Pump (BCP); and that the BCP is much more complex than previously thought. The most common themes emerging from this question showed that respondents recognise the ocean as a carbon sink and the role of the biological elements in the carbon cycle.

Box 3.1 Themes of the responses to the question: “What comes to mind when you hear the term ocean carbon?” (with the number of unique times a theme was mentioned). 13 responses.

- Carbon sequestration and the ocean as a sink for carbon (9)
- The role of living ocean species and habitats including ‘blue carbon habitats’ (8)
- Industry and emissions (4)
- The role of non-living elements in storing carbon (3)
- Ocean acidification (2)
- Climate regulation (1)
- Seabed disturbance (1)
- Large scale (1)
- Complexity, uncertainty, lack of knowledge and understanding (1)
- Greenwashing (1)

All respondents thought that the ocean is extremely or very important for helping us to manage or improve climate change (Figure 3.1). One respondent referred to the ocean as our largest natural sink for carbon.

Seventy-seven percent of respondents thought that the links between carbon and fishing have a lot or a great deal of importance important for understanding the Biological Carbon Pump and/or climate change, while 23% thought these links are moderately important (Figure 3.2). One respondent emphasised that fishing is not the only activity introducing pressures in the marine environment and interacting with ocean carbon.

Figure 3.1 Responses to the question: “How important is the ocean for helping us to manage or improve climate change?” (13 responses).

Figure 3.2 Responses to the question: “How important are the links between carbon and fishing for understanding the Biological Carbon Pump and/or climate change?” (13 responses).

In terms of the ways respondents thought that ocean carbon affects fishing (Box 3.2), the most common responses related to impacts of climate change on fisheries. Some also thought about the potential impacts new management measures related to climate mitigation may have on fisheries. In terms of the ways fishing can affect ocean carbon (Box 3.3), respondents thought about the impacts of seabed disturbance; the role of emissions from the fishing industry; and the impacts of changes to food webs on the carbon cycle.

Box 3.2 Themes of the responses to the question: “*In what ways do you think ocean carbon affects fishing?*” 12 responses.

- Impacts of climate change and atmospheric CO₂, including temperature, and acidification, on fish, shellfish and fisheries, including distribution, behaviour and abundance of fish and foodwebs (8)
- Management measures of climate mitigation measures potentially resulting in changes to fishing practices including related to fuel, gear and effort (3)
- Phytoplankton and primary productivity, that can change due to carbon, as the base of the foodweb, affecting fish distribution, etc. (2)
- Fishing as a food source and other methods of food production introduce potentially more carbon (2)

Box 3.3 Themes of the responses to the question: “*In what ways do you think fishing affects ocean carbon?*” 13 responses.

- Disturbance of seabed due to trawling and other factors, with potential release of carbon from sediments and/or loss or damage of habitats that sequester or store carbon (8)
- Carbon emissions to atmosphere and fuel use (8)
- Removal of fish biomass including resulting changes to food webs, carbon storage, carbon flux, carbon pump, and impacts of bycatch (6)
- Ecosystem disruption (1)
- Sustainable fishing is an opportunity for low carbon food source (1)
- Uncertainty around some aspects e.g. bycatch, impact of trawling on seabed (2)

About half of respondents (54%) were only moderately concerned about the carbon footprint of fishing, while the rest were concerned or very concerned (Figure 3.3). Emissions and sediment disturbance were the factors most respondents attributed to the carbon footprint of fishing (Box 3.4). One respondent mentioned a lack of evidence on the carbon footprint of fishing, and another mentioned that they would be more worried by an industry such as aviation.

Figure 3.3 Responses to the question: “How concerned are you about the carbon footprint of fishing?” (13 responses).

Box 3.4 Themes of the responses to the question: “What aspect of fishing do you think are most important for its carbon footprint?” 12 responses.

- Fuel emissions including due to fuel intensive activities and propulsion (8)
- Sediment disturbance and release of stored carbon from seabed, including through bottom trawling (7)
- Removal of biomass of fish (1)
- Refrigerant loss (1)
- Shellfish farming (1)

Around 70% of respondents were concerned or very concerned about bottom trawling releasing carbon from sediments (Figure 3.4). Two respondents highlighted the need for more evidence in regard to this question and where management might come in to play. One of these asked about the impacts on historically trawled grounds compared to new sites, and what impact displacement may have. Another respondent asked about the impacts of natural movement of sediments.

Figure 3.4 Responses to the question: “How concerned are you about the fact that bottom trawling can cause carbon to be released from sediments?” (13 responses).

Plankton including phyto- and zooplankton, and macroalgae and macrophyte blue carbon habitats, were the biological components most frequently mentioned by respondents as being important for capturing and storing carbon (Box 3.5). In addition, reef habitats and large marine mammals were also mentioned.

Sixty-two percent of respondents were concerned or very concerned that removing fish, other animals, plants and algae (like seaweed or plankton) from the ocean removes ocean carbon, while 23% were moderately concerned, and 16% were not at all or only a little concerned (Figure 3.5). Two

respondents noted that this is a terrestrial as well as a marine issue, with one noting that evidence is lacking on this.

Box 3.5 Themes of the responses to the question: “What comes to mind when you think about the living organisms important for capturing and storing ocean carbon?” 13 responses.

- Phytoplankton/plankton (6)
- Seagrasses, macroalgae, mangroves, salt marsh (6)
- Reefs, including oyster reefs (4)
- Whales/Cetaceans (4)
- All living organisms, trophic levels (3)
- Fish (2)
- Mudflats (1)

Figure 3.5 Responses to the question: “How concerned are you that removing fish, other animals, plants and algae (like seaweed or plankton) from the ocean removes ocean carbon?” (13 respondents).

Offshore renewable energy was the marine activity most commonly mentioned as something new or growing (Box 3.6) and was mentioned from both positive (meeting climate targets) and negative perspectives (interfering with fisheries). Seventy-five percent of respondents were at least moderately concerned about new marine activities (Figure 3.5). Three respondents mentioned the need to understand what is currently happening in the marine environment, and what impacts new activities would have, with one of these emphasising the need to consider all relevant impacts from a broad perspective.

Box 3.6 Themes of the responses to the question: “Are you aware of any new or growing marine activities that are related to carbon and climate change? (Which ones)” (11 responses).

- Offshore marine renewable energy, wind energy: respondents mentioned the need to meet climate targets, but also the relative benefits of this in terms of overall carbon budget, and placement (5)
- Carbon capture and storage technologies (2)
- Conservation and restoration (2)
- None/not really (2)
- Dredging (1)
- Aggregate extraction (1)
- Seaweed harvesting (1)
- Deep-sea mining (1)

Figure 3.5 Responses to the question: “How concerned are you about these activities?” (12 responses).

The most common response to whether there would be implications for respondents’ work was related to new or changing policies, and that respondents would need to react to this in their jobs (Box 3.7). Other issues that respondents wanted to address were related to socio-economic concerns including the potential for job losses and impacts of climate change on coastal communities; the role of MPAs; and the role of aquaculture (Box 3.8).

Box 3.7 Themes of the responses to the question: “Based on your responses to the previous questions, will there be implications for you in your work? (e.g. changes to your practices, policies, focal areas, etc.) (Briefly describe)” (13 responses).

- The need to respond to changing or new policies (8)
- Need to increase knowledge and understanding to anticipate upcoming issues and challenges (2)
- New outputs/products required (e.g. type of data, case studies, etc.) (1)

Box 3.8 Are there any other topics related to fishing and ocean carbon, not covered in this survey, that are of interest/concern to you? Briefly describe:

- Job losses (1)
- Impact of climate change on coastal communities, including fisheries (1)
- Role of MPAs (1)
- Use of fodder fish for finfish farms (1)

3.2 Shelf Seas Fisheries – Ocean Carbon Social Ecological System

One of the goals of the workshop was to produce a mental model, together with the stakeholders, of the elements of a shelf seas fisheries – ocean carbon system and the interactions between those elements. The first step of this was to brainstorm on what elements should be included. This was followed by building the model through discussion of how the elements interact. This type of mental map is a causal model of the system, represented by a network of elements and the relationships between them (Barbrook-Johnson and Penn, 2022). The connections should capture all the complexity in the systems, but notes or annotations can also be used to represent different beliefs. This type of approach is an iterative process, and the map can be built on and further developed over time.

3.2.1 Elements of a Shelf Seas System

In the first step, we identified the elements of the shelf seas fisheries – ocean carbon system to include in the mental model, and to support an ocean carbon risk assessment. The elements were structured around the categories: sectors, pressures, ecosystem components and ecosystem services or socio-economic factors. Participants of the workshop were asked four questions, in turn:

- What sectors are most relevant in relation to ocean carbon in the shelf seas?
- What pressures are most relevant in relation to ocean carbon in the shelf seas?
- What ecosystem elements should be included in the analyses? At what level of detail?
- What ecosystem services and socio-economic factors should be included in the model? i.e. what are the trade-offs you are concerned about?

Participants could suggest their responses through MS Teams polls for each question. The polls appeared as live Word Clouds that participants could view (Figure 3.6). After a first round of answers, prompts (Appendix 8.5) were shown to participants to identify if there were other categories that they would add or remove from these lists. The final list per category can be seen in Table 3.1.

Figure 3.6 Word clouds of elements of the shelf-seas ocean carbon social-ecological system, as chosen by participants of the workshop. See Table 3.1 for full lists of elements. Elements are categorised under: sectors (or human activities), pressures (mechanisms of change), ecosystem components, and ecosystem services/socio-economic elements.

Table 3.1 Full list of components proposed by participants.

Sector	Mentions
Fishing (including trawling, nets, pots and traps)	17
Offshore Renewable Energy (ORE)	13
Conservation/MPAs/Restoration	9
Aquaculture (including seaweed and bivalves)	8
Shipping/Transportation/ Short Sea Shipping	7
Land-based activities including agriculture, urban, sewage, pollution	7
Tourism and Recreation	4
Aggregate Extraction	2
Mining	2
Others: Dredging; Oil & Gas; Cable laying	1 mention each
Pressure	Mentions
Habitat disturbance and loss including seabed disturbance, erosion, anchorage, foundations, construction, habitat degradation and coastal squeeze	13
Pressures from fishing, trawling and dredging	11
Climate change	8
Pollution including sewage, plastic, river discharge, eutrophication	8
Acidification	5
Extraction of biomass/species	4
Temperature (warming)	3
Storms	2
Pressures from ORE	2
Others: Sea level rise; Pressures from shipping; Pressures from recreation; Spatial pressures; Policy related; Social; Economic; Human population; Environmental; Habitat policy	1 mention each
Ecosystem component	Mentions
Fish (including forage, pelagic, demersal)	11
Seagrass, Macroalgae incl. Kelp forest, Mangrove, Blue Carbon Habitats	10
Phyto- and zooplankton (including viruses, bacteria)	7
Predator-prey interactions/Trophic Levels	6
Mammals	5
Seabed, sediment habitats, mudflats	5
Habitats	4
Reefs including coral	4
Benthic species/communities	3
Species	2
Others: Invertebrates; Water column; Elasmobranchs; Broad species groups; Birds; Riparian inputs; Salinity; Depth; Microbiome; Low trophic species; Human inputs; Eunis L5-6; In line with current monitoring e.g. indicator framework	1 mention each
Ecosystem service/socio-economic factor	Mentions
Habitats and biodiversity (impacts) including related to food webs, spawning grounds	10
Food (provision, supply, supply chain, security, price)	9
Livelihoods including job losses, specific fishery dependencies (inshore, small scale, trawling, low impact), sectoral sustainability	8
Fishing including inshore, trawling	5
Local community impacts	5
Climate regulation and carbon sequestration	4
Tourism and recreation	4
ORE	3
(loss of) Fishing grounds	3
MPAs/protected sites	3
Restoration	2
Others: Spatial squeeze; Vilification of groups/industries; Security; Fairness/equity; Water quality; Healthy fisheries; Fuel price; Primary producers; Knowledge; Coastal protection	1 mention each

3.2.2 Ocean Carbon – Fisheries System Components Discussion

Participants questions and comments are given in an anonymised form in black text. The response from the Marine Institute (MI)/OceanICU researchers is given in blue. In some cases, additional information has been added since the workshop, this is indicated in *italics*.

- Should we keep all the proposed elements along with elements that have been suggested by participants? Yes.
- Should Seabed mining be added? Seabed mining is included in the high seas assessments and meeting, but not shelf seas as it is not a shelf sea issue.
- Should precipitation change, e.g. a change in storm activity be included? Yes, the regularity of storms is relevant and could be included.
- A lot of the pressure list come under land-based emissions, such as litter, organic matter, radionuclides etc. entering via rivers etc. How will eutrophication and warming seas affect trophic levels in marine ecosystems? Agreed, lots of marine pressures stem from land-based activities. The importance of land-sea interactions has been previously highlighted. We anticipate our efforts will focus on the quantification of (direct) impacts relating to the ocean carbon cycle rather than carbon credits on land or global cycle as a whole (indirect effects).
- General consensus that the ecosystem components should be kept quite high-level and broad.
- Marine mammals should be split into functional groups, they are very different in their roles and we don't know how they contribute to carbon at shelf level. Most important split is filter-feeders vs toothed mammals.

3.2.3 Conceptual Model of a Shelf Seas Fisheries-Ocean Carbon System

The elements from the first exercise were used as a starting point to build the conceptual model ensuring the inclusion of the focal elements: ‘fishing’ and ‘ocean C cycle’ and ‘global C cycle’. This was produced live during the workshop via the online MentalModeler software (www.mentalmodeler.org; Gray et al. 2013). Discussion with the participants informed where links should be (i.e. what connections exist). Through this process, the elements in the model evolved, and understanding of the linkages was elucidated. This resulting model is illustrated in Figure 3.7.

Figure 3.7 Provisional mental model co-produced with stakeholders during the shelf seas workshop using the software MentalModeler. The elements of the model are represented as boxes and colour indicates the type of element: sectors (orange), pressures (blue), ecosystem components (green), ecosystem services (yellow), socio-economic elements (pink). Grey boxes are elements that can be mechanisms of change but are not necessarily pressures. Links between the nodes are represented by lines. Lines are either positive (elements are positively correlated; blue lines), negative (elements have an inverse relationship; red lines), or unknown (thin black lines). Note: full consistency check of this model is in progress, some amendments may result from this process.

The elements included in the final model were:

Sectors	Pressures	Ecosystem Components	Socio-economic elements & Ecosystem Services	Climate
Fishing	Emissions	Habitats	Food provisioning	Hydrodynamic Changes
Shipping/Transport	Organic matter	Fish	Clean Energy	Climate Change
Aquaculture	Seabed impacts		Climate Regulation	Ocean Carbon Cycle
Offshore Renewable Energy (ORE)	Species extraction		Displacement	Global Carbon Cycle
	Artificial Habitat			

4. Celtic Seas Socio-Economic Interactions

4.1 Recap on previous Mission Atlantic Celtic Seas workshop

Dr Pedreschi gave a brief introduction to the Mission Atlantic project, including an introduction to Integrated Ecosystem Management (IEA). Mission Atlantic stakeholders previously co-created a conceptual model focusing on offshore renewable energy (ORE) development, conservation measures (MPAs) and fisheries (Figure 4.1). Analysis of this model, coupled with scenario development and iterative stakeholder engagement highlighted that the potential impacts and trade-offs associated with the proposed scenarios would like lead to socio-economic impacts that were not well captured by the current suite of modelling tools. As such, an additional workshop was planned to identify where interactions are likely to occur, improve understanding of how socio-economic impacts may be realised, and how they connect to the ecological system, and to document additional data sources that may facilitate the quantification of impacts.

Figure 4.1 The original Celtic Sea conceptual model developed with stakeholders. The red box highlights the socio-economic aspects of the system.

4.2 Celtic Seas Socio-Economic System Conceptual Model

The initial model elements (red box Fig 4.1) were presented to the stakeholders and a moderated discussion enabled the further elaboration of linkages, missing elements, interactions, and outcomes resulting in an improved socio-economic mental model (Figure 4.2). The resulting consensus model illustrates the potential relationships and impact pathways when considering the interactions of fishing, offshore renewable energy and conservation (primarily via protected areas).

Figure 4.2 Provisional mental model co-produced with stakeholders during the workshop. The elements of the model are represented as boxes and colour indicates the type of element illustrated in the legend. Links between the nodes are represented by lines which can be positive (elements are positively correlated; blue lines), negative (elements have an inverse relationship; red lines), or unknown (thin black lines). Note: full consistency check of this model is in progress, some amendments may result from this process.

Participants highlighted that the nature of both the windfarms and the protected areas (in terms of scale, structure, access, restrictions, etc.) will ultimately dictate eventual impacts, and for almost all aspects discussed here, there is little certainty on the form they will ultimately take. As such it was highlighted that this model needs to be flexible and adaptable, and iteratively reviewed to be able to capture the range of impacts that may potentially, and actually do, occur as this field develops. Nevertheless, a range of social, economic, cultural, and ecosystem service interactions were identified. Future scenario investigations aim to identify the direction and scale of impacts, and potential trade-offs that are likely to occur.

4.3 Socio-economic conceptual model Discussion

The extensive discussions to form the model were documented, and the outcomes are illustrated in the previous section. Additional participant questions and comments are provided below in an anonymised form in black text. The response from the Marine Institute (MI)/Mission Atlantic researchers is given in blue. In some cases, additional information has been added since the workshop, this is indicated in *italics*.

- Are you quantifying or prioritising which element is more important in the long term? Food provision you would imagine would be the most important of all and a priority for many countries in the future. Should we be looking at that going forward? Especially in Ireland where we have such a large marine resource. We are looking to find where the biggest impacts are, and what we are missing. For example, both fishing and renewables produce employment, but what will the changes be, e.g. in terms of jobs and/or community perspectives. This model is about capturing what is

[likely to be] affected and then investigating [e.g. via scenarios] what elements would be impacted the most, and understanding the linkages between them.

- Could you just clarify what diversification means in this? In this context we mean diversification of fishers away from fishing into new jobs (e.g. into renewable jobs). Diversification can also relate to the change in the make-up of the fleet/crew, for example with more non-national workers.
- Possibly another link to fishing and diversification from extractive fishing to algae farming, another diversification for the fishers possibly linked to a reduction in stocks and stock movements they may need to diversify from traditional targets. A complete change in mind-set would be required.
- From the fishing industry side, it's hard to see where we are going to exist at all when you take in restricted fishing, prohibited areas, and areas for OREs that could possibly be no-take or highly restricted for fishing, so where are we going to stay fishing? That's important. Restricted fishing and full exclusion would form displacement and impact the fishing industry and community.
- Will this structure be adaptable to changes if you develop a model here, can the weighting of each section change? Yes, as things become clearer, we can focus on the realities of the situation. This is an evolving model.
- There have been claims [from the ORE industry] that there will be no restriction on fishing in windfarms but there will be. It might be possible for a boat with mobile gear straight through a windfarm but no capacity to turn if something went wrong. Hard to share the space with other vessels too. Any fishing that could take place would be very restrictive, especially with safety concerns etc.

5. Action Items

Action points arising from the meeting

- Summary report to be written and circulated for review and feedback.
- The models (Figure 3.7 and 4.2) will be consistency checked for anomalies and issues, and ground-truthed against available evidence and in consultation with stakeholders in a future session.
- The researchers will continue to search for appropriate data sources on socio-economic aspects, and reiterate their appeal to participants to provide any resources they think may be relevant.
- For OceanICU, additional workshops will be arranged with shelf seas and deep-sea mining stakeholders, and follow-up meetings with this stakeholder group.
- For Mission Atlantic, follow-up meeting will be arranged to report on outcomes.

6. Conclusions

Active engagement from the invited participants led to a successful outcome for the workshop. Through discussion, survey results and building the conceptual models, some key themes emerged relating to ocean carbon. These are;

Themes:

- **Importance of Blue Carbon Habitats:** The role of the ocean and the ecosystem services provided by habitats in sequestering carbon need to be recognised, along with the implications of loss and damage to blue carbon habitats for biodiversity and climate change.
- **Fisheries and Climate Change:** The impacts of climate change on fisheries, how carbon will affect the food web and the implications of these changes for fisheries, and how fisheries can adapt to climate change.
- **Food security:** The role of fishing in providing food security needs to be fully recognised. Management of ocean carbon need to be balanced against the seafood service fish and fisheries are providing (trade-offs).
- **Climate Policy:** Changing policies relating to ocean carbon have wide ranging implications affecting eNGOs, management, as well as the fishing industry.
- **Offshore Renewable Energy:** There are currently high levels of uncertainty relating to ORE. For example, spatial displacement of fishing and shipping vessels may have implications for carbon (e.g. through having to travel further).
- **Livelihoods and Communities:** The potential impacts on particular groups (inshore fishers, trawlers) and on local coastal communities require consideration and consultation in the development of carbon management and policy.

Key knowledge and evidence gaps were also highlighted as a key issue. These related to the lack of consistent evidence on the effects of seabed trawling on carbon, specifically around the release of carbon from sediments. Additionally, the process of building the carbon conceptual model highlighted for some of the participants the uncertainty around the potential impacts resulting from changes to the ocean carbon cycle due to marine activities, and how these would relate to changes to the global carbon cycle, and ultimately climate change.

The above points and themes will guide the direction of our research going forward in OceanICU. They will help form the basis of scenarios to test using a range of modelling approaches, including Bayesian Belief Networks (BBN), and help inform the basis of an ecological risk assessment centred around carbon.

The second conceptual model will help to improve our understanding of how fishing, ORE and conservation may interact to create socio-economic impacts and outcomes. The discussion will inform our work moving forward in the Mission Atlantic project. Future results and outcomes will be reported back to the participants and wider stakeholder group.

7. References

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8. Appendices

8.1 Agenda

Time (GMT)	Program
PART ONE: Morning session, OceanICU project	
09.00 – 09.30	Introduction to workshop, housekeeping and OceanICU project
09.30 – 09.40	Results from the pre-workshop survey
09.40 – 10.40	Presentation and open discussion on shelf seas fisheries and ocean carbon
10.40 - 11.00	Exercise: elements of an ocean carbon-shelf seas fisheries system
11.00 – 11.20	Break
11.20 – 13.00	Exercise: co-producing a model of an ocean carbon-shelf seas fisheries system
13.00 – 14.00	Lunch
PART TWO: Afternoon session, Mission Atlantic project	
14.00 – 14.40	Introduction to Mission Atlantic and socio-economic aspects
14.40 - 15.00	Q&A
15.00 – 15.20	Break
15.20 – 16.45	Exercise: building on co-produced socio-economic model
16.45 – 17.00	Wrap up and final words

8.2 Acronyms

- BCP: Biological Carbon Pump
- CDR: Carbon Dioxide Removal
- CO₂: Carbon dioxide
- DST: Decision Support Tool
- DST: Decision Support Tool
- EBFM: Ecosystem-Based Fisheries Management
- EBM: Ecosystem-Based Management
- ES: Ecosystem Services
- FPO: Fish Producers Organisation
- HVO: Hydrotreated Vegetable Oil
- ICES: International Council for the Exploration of the Sea
- IPCC: Intergovernmental Panel on Climate Change
- ISE FPO: Irish South and East Fish Producers Organisation
- IWDG: Irish Whale and Dolphin Group
- MMO: Marine Management Organisation
- NET: Negative Emissions Technologies
- NIFF: National Inshore Fisheries Forum
- NWWAC: North Western Waters Advisory Council
- OceanICU project: <https://ocean-icu.eu/>
- SST: Sea Surface Temperature
- SWAN: Sustainable Water Network
- UCC: University College Cork

8.3 List of Organisations Represented by Workshop Attendees

Participant	Institute
1	Marine Planning Policy and Legislation, Department of Housing, Local Government and Heritage
2	Irish Seal Sanctuary
3	Marine Management Organisation
4	Marine Management Organisation
5	Marine Management Organisation
6	BirdWatch Ireland
7	Seafish
8	Sustainable Water Network (SWAN)
9	Northern Ireland Marine Task Force
10	Northern Ireland Marine Taskforce
11	MaREI Centre, ERI: Beaufort Building, University College Cork
12	Marine Institute
13	Irish South and East Fish Producers Organisation
14	North Western Waters Advisory Council (NWWAC)
15	NWWAC
16	The Irish Wildlife Trust
17	Consultant to The Pew Charitable Trusts
18	Irish Whale and Dolphin Group
19	Marine Institute
20	NIFF

8.4 Resources

- Atwood et al 2020 Global patterns in marine sediment carbon stocks. *Frontiers in Marine Science*, 7 <https://www.frontiersin.org/articles/10.3389/fmars.2020.00165/full>
- Costello (2024) Evidence of economic benefits from marine protected areas. *Scientia Marina* 88(1) DOI: <https://doi.org/10.3989/scimar.05417.080>
- Decarbonising the Fishing Sector report: [https://www.europarl.europa.eu/RegData/etudes/STUD/2023/740225/EPRS_STU\(2023\)740225_EN.pdf](https://www.europarl.europa.eu/RegData/etudes/STUD/2023/740225/EPRS_STU(2023)740225_EN.pdf)
- EBFA's page on science, including references to carbon: <https://bottomfishingalliance.eu/latest-scientific-news/>
- Epstein, G., Middelburg, J. J., Hawkins, J. P., Norris, C. R., & Roberts, C. M. (2022). The impact of mobile demersal fishing on carbon storage in seabed sediments. *Global Change Biology*, 28(9), 2875-2894. <https://doi.org/10.1111/gcb.16105>
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- ICES workshop on Assessing the Impact of Fishing on Oceanic Carbon (WKFISHCARBON; outputs from 2023 meeting): https://ices-library.figshare.com/articles/report/Workshop_on_Assessing_the_Impact_of_Fishing_on_Oceanic_Carbon_WKFISHCARBON_outputs_from_2023_meeting_/24949122
- MPA Atlas: <https://mpatlas.org/>
- OceanICU webinars (including Fish, Fisheries and Carbon webinar): <https://ocean-icu.eu/webinars/>
- OceanICU: <https://ocean-icu.eu/>
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- Stakeholder Mailing List Sign Up for OceanICU <https://tinyurl.com/OceanICUjoin>
- The Guardian: Bottom trawling releases as much carbon as air travel, landmark study finds: <https://www.theguardian.com/environment/2021/mar/17/trawling-for-fish-releases-as-much-carbon-as-air-travel-report-finds-climate-crisis>
- The Guardian: Carbon released by bottom trawling 'too big to ignore', says study <https://www.theguardian.com/environment/2024/jan/18/carbon-released-by-bottom-trawling-too-big-to-ignore-says-study>
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8.5 Socio-ecological system Components

Sectors

Agriculture
Fishing
Land-based Industry
Military
Nuclear
Research
Shipping
Telecommunications
Tourism/Recreation
Waste Water
Dredging
Ocean NETS/CDR
Aquaculture

Pressures

Abrasion
Bycatch
Contaminating Compounds
Electromagnetic Fields
Incidental Loss
Invasive Species
Litter
Noise
Extraction of Non-living Resources
Organic Matter
Radionuclides
Sealing
Siltation/Smothering
Species Extraction
Thermal changes
GHG emissions (to air)
pH changes
Salinity changes
Death/injury by collision
Precipitation changes

Ecosystem Components

Cephalopods
Demersal Elasmobranchs
Demersal Fish
Pelagic Elasmobranchs
Pelagic Fish
Reptiles
Seabirds
Marine Mammals
Epipelagic
Littoral Soft Sediment
Littoral Rock and Reef
Shallow Soft Sediment
Shallow Rock and Reef
Shelf Soft Sediment
Shelf Rock and Reef

Ecosystem Services

Seafood - wild
Seafood - Aquaculture
Raw materials (Biotic/Abiotic)
Genetic Materials
Nursery populations and habitats
Refuge habitats
Global climate regulation
Feeding grounds
Chemical composition of oceans and atmosphere
Cultural services

Socio-Economic Factors

Wages
Fish prices
Fuel prices
Gentrification
Fleet diversification
Safety at Sea
Equity
Quota
Management
Governance
Enforcement
Fishing Behaviour
Community Impacts
Processing/Processors
Livelihoods
Policy